

DEVELOPMENT OF DRIFTING BUOY SYSTEMS FOR OCEANOGRAPHIC AND METEOROLOGICAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

During the last decade, the launch of a series of polar-orbiting satellites to be used for climatological studies, and also capable of surface platform position location and data telemetry, prompted the development of relatively low-cost oceanographic and meteorological drifting buoy measurement platforms to support a wide spectrum of scientific and observational programs. The feasibility of economically and reliably deploying meteorological drifting buoys in remote data-sparse areas of the world has been amply demonstrated in the recent Global Weather Experiment. Drifting buoy technology will play an increasingly important role in climate-related research programs during the next decade. The role of drifting buoy data in improving weather analysis and forecasts may be a dominant factor in the development of operational drifting buoy systems. Development programs are underway or in planning to upgrade the measurement capabilities of the present drifting buoy systems in response to anticipated future demands.

1. INTRODUCTION

The NOAA Data Buoy Office (NDBO) has been actively engaged in the development of drifting buoy measurement systems capable of supporting various scientific experiments and environmental monitoring programs. This paper discusses the essential features of the comprehensive development efforts in the area of meteorological and oceanographic drifting buoy systems.

Drifting buoy data users include oceanographic and atmospheric scientists. Recent applications for drifting buoy systems have included: The Equatorial Pacific Ocean Climate Studies (EPOCS), the First GARP Global Experiment (FGGE), Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion (OTEC), and other energy-related offshore environmental monitoring programs. Potential applications for these systems include: the Storm Transfer and Response Experiment (STREX), the Ocean Heat Transport and Storage Experiment (OHTSE), the Global Ocean Circulation Experiment (GOCE), planned climate-related research experiments in support of the U.S. Climate Program, and the operational use of drifting buoys to provide meteorological data from data-sparse regions for weather analysis and forecast enhancement.

Many of these scientific and operational programs require environmental data in areas where surface observations can only

be made in a cost-effective manner from small, expendable, drifting meteorological and oceanographic buoys. The technology development underway provides broad, coordinated development support for these and other programs. The number and diversity of these experiments often make it difficult to identify hardware developments which will meet their needs while keeping the cost to a level commensurate with the importance and value of each experiment. NDBO is playing a strong role in conducting these technological developments to eliminate costly duplicative work without seriously compromising the goals and measurement requirements of the various users. The approach used has been to fund the common denominators in the many hardware requirements and through development activities, to assist the scientific community in meeting their program objectives with a minimum of duplication and an optimum use of federal funds.

Requirements for drifting buoys at the present time fall into meteorological and oceanographic types based on the application for which they are intended. A meteorological drifting buoy reports a simple set of meteorological variables, is used in sufficiently large numbers to provide a field description of these variables, and is deployed on a grid spacing to define synoptic and larger scale meteorological systems. During the recent Global Weather Experiment,¹ an array of approximately 300 meteorological drifting buoys was deployed in the Southern Oceans to provide surface level pressure and sea surface temperature. The data were used primarily to provide a surface reference level to improve recovery of temperature profiles from remote satellite measurements.² An unexpected result of the data available from the data-sparse southern hemisphere was the impact on improved weather forecasts by the Australian National Meteorological Analysis Centre, Bureau of Meteorology in Melbourne. The impact of these data was extremely valuable and substantial in overcoming forecasting problems arising from the deficiency of surface observations in the oceans of the southern hemisphere.³ This unexpected success in the use of drifting buoy data for improving weather forecasts has prompted investigators in the U.S. to plan an experiment in the Northeast Pacific, to study the feasibility of using drifting meteorological buoy data from data-sparse regions to improve weather forecasts.

An oceanographic drifting buoy is generally configured as a Lagrangian measurement device. A Lagrangian drifter, whose prime measurement objective is the buoy trajectory itself, is used in experiments that are both spatial and time-sequences in nature. Other oceanographic drifting buoys are in a non-

Lagrangian configuration, i.e., the position variable, while needed to locate the data source, is not used to provide a trajectory of water mass. A buoy used to measure subsurface temperature, or a relatively high capability drifting buoy to be used for air-sea interaction experiments are examples of this later category of drifting buoys. It is expected that meteorological and oceanographic drifting buoys will be significant measurement elements in an anticipated emerging global observing system to support the United States climate program.⁴

The individual elements comprising a buoy system can be identified by the following major systems elements: hull, power, sensors, control electronics, telemetry, and in the case of a Lagrangian buoy, a drogue device to provide Lagrangian-tracking capability. In all of the applications, a nonsynoptic data set is achieved because polar-orbiting satellites are used for data telemetry and drifting buoy position determination. The NIMBUS-F satellite launched in 1975, the TIROS-N satellite launched in 1978, and the NOAA-A satellite launched in 1979, are the polar-orbiting satellites used in present drifting buoy applications. The satellite systems developed have been designed to minimize the complexity of the telemetry and position determination electronics needed on the drifting buoys or other platforms. Simplification of the buoy electronics allowed the development of relatively low-cost drifting buoy systems which are considered expendable for most applications.

NDBO is involved in a broad spectrum of drifting buoy technology development programs, and each of these activities is briefly covered. The central emphasis in this paper is the development of a meteorological drifting buoy for application in the Global Weather Experiment; however, technology development activities for future programs are discussed. NDBO experiences, problems encountered, and programs for future developments are discussed.

2. DEVELOPMENT PLANS

Figure 1 shows the overall development plan for drifting buoys during the next several years. Each development activity is shown with the essential features of the ongoing and planned activities in these areas. The system capabilities required to meet the various program objectives and associated schedules are shown. To provide a reference starting point for planned activities, the time sequence of the development of the basic meteorological drifting buoy for the Global Weather Experiment is shown. An important element of each planned development activity is extensive laboratory field testing of prototype systems for engineering and scientific evaluation prior to operational applications. In many applications, an early field experiment is used to evaluate prototype hardware in an ongoing evolutionary technology development process. It has been often demonstrated that deployment of drifting buoy systems

Figure 1. Drifting Buoy Technology Development

in a field operation, and participation in an experiment, leads to hardware design improvements that cannot be determined by laboratory or simulated observations alone. These engineering/science tests are a major area of interaction between development programs at NDBO and the user community supported by these activities.

2.1 Meteorological Drifting Buoys

During the past several years, the Global Weather Experiment was the major impetus for drifting buoy technology development. As shown in Figure 1, a buoy capable of measuring a basic set of simple meteorological parameters was developed to be used in this major scientific endeavor to study the physical processes in the troposphere and the stratosphere. The buoy measures barometric pressure and sea surface temperature, is capable of survival in a severe environment, and can be deployed by ship or aircraft. Barometric pressure was the critical measurement required and a significant development effort

was expended to develop and test a suitable pressure port and vent system, and to select a suitable sensor with long-term stability after deployment and for prolonged operation at sea.

An important aspect of the Global Weather Experiment was the observation of near-surface conditions (barometric pressure and sea surface temperature) with a system of low-cost, expendable drifting buoys, communicating via polar-orbiting satellites (TIROS-N and NOAA-6). The buoy transmits signals which are received on a random access basis (without interrogation) by the satellite. The transmitted data is stored by the satellite, together with sufficient information about the apparent carrier frequency of the buoy transmission to enable the relative velocity between the buoy and the satellite to be computed, which, in turn, permits the determination of buoy position.

Figure 2 shows a schematic picture of the meteorological drifting buoy developed for use during the Global Weather Experiment. The U.S. deployed 64 buoys during the experiment,

Figure 2. FGGE Meteorological Drifting Buoy

and good performance was achieved. Performance statistics indicate that 40 percent of the buoys can be expected to be operational after one year, the design life of the drifting buoy system.

As shown in Figure 1, the major future technology development thrust in the area of meteorological drifting buoys will be to provide the capability to measure wind speed and direction, and possibly air temperature. An important near-term application of these measurement capabilities will be in a series of feasibility demonstrations, to determine the effectiveness of meteorological drifting buoys to provide data from data-sparse regions to improve weather forecast capabilities. The first of a series of feasibility demonstrations is planned for the latter part of 1980 to be performed in the Northeast Pacific near the present location of Ocean Station PAPA.

With the future availability of increased meteorological measurement capability, drifting buoys will play an increasingly important role in oceanographic and meteorological heat budget experiments covering large ocean areas during the next decade. The programs have two aspects, i.e., understanding the physical processes which lead to long-term variability in heat storage and its effect on atmosphere, and monitoring this variability over long periods of time. Both of these present formidable observational difficulties in the light of the large spatial coverage and density of observations required. A wide variety of observational systems will undoubtedly be used, including ships, specialized platforms, and anchored deep ocean data buoys.⁵ However, availability and expense associated with these systems will limit their use. Drifting buoys will be used to augment the spatial and temporal measurement requirements for these global climate-related programs.

2.2 Lagrangian/Oceanographic Drifting Buoys

It is well recognized that the measurement of surface layer ocean currents is of considerable importance to oceanographers and meteorologists studying the role of the ocean in heat transport and storage.^{6 7 8} As in the atmosphere, understanding and monitoring the general circulation of the ocean is an important step toward understanding and predicting the climate. Although the general circulation has been studied for many years, there is no definitive picture of the global movement of water, which to a large degree controls the flux of heat energy. Consequently, as an adjunct to the meteorological drifting buoy development, a Lagrangian buoy development program has been undertaken to meet oceanographic measurement objectives. The approach NDBO has taken is to modify the basic meteorological drifting buoy hull configuration with the addition of a drogue device to achieve a Lagrangian tracking capability. Laboratory studies have led to the development of two primary drogue devices. They include a simple window shade drogue and a vertically oriented, wind sock-type drogue device.

An important outcome of the drifting buoy technology program has been the development of a computer time domain numerical model to aid in the design of drifting buoy systems. With the model, the motions of a drifting buoy system can be studied in a simulated environment and the critical engineering parameters needed for design synthesis can be determined. The model simulation capability is used extensively to predict the capability of a Lagrangian drifting buoy to measure the

velocity of a parcel of water in which the drifting buoy system is embedded. The Lagrangian "effectiveness" and an understanding of Lagrangian measurement performance is an important element in the design of Lagrangian measurement systems. As shown in Figure 1, future development activities planned at NDBO relate to the improvement of the numerical model prediction capability by performing field Lagrangian comparison experiments to validate model performance.

Long-term ocean monitoring will be an important element of climate research and prediction programs as contained within the planned National Climate Program; to promote capabilities to understand and respond to natural and man-induced climate processes and their implications.⁹ Sea surface temperature is a key oceanographic parameter because it controls the transfer of thermal energy from the ocean to the atmosphere having a direct and immediate effect on the climate system. In order to understand and eventually predict large-scale, long-term variability of sea surface temperature, it will be necessary to monitor the heat content of the upper "heat storage" layer of the ocean. The heat content of the upper layer of the ocean can be determined by obtaining the vertical profile of temperature down to a baseline depth or temperature. In conjunction with other measurement systems, including remote satellite measurements, it is anticipated that drifting buoys with a subsurface temperature measurement capability will be used as a measurement/monitoring platform.¹⁰ Initial development activities leading to the test of engineering prototype drifting buoys with thermistor strings for subsurface temperature measurements were not an outstanding success. Hardware failure combinations ranging from sensor line to electronics resulted in a maximum buoy life of 170 days among three prototype systems. An energetic technology development program is now underway based on extensive laboratory testing to solve critical mechanical problems hampering the long-life expectancy of these systems. Three engineering prototype systems, capable of ship or air deployment, will be field tested this year upon completion of the development program.

3. EXPERIENCE

The development of satellite systems capable of providing data telemetry and position determination from any portion of the globe has provided the facility for the use of low-cost drifting buoy systems independent of the support of tracking ships, aircraft or near-land stations. A series of satellite systems such as the NIMBUS-4, EOLE, and NIMBUS-F have led to the operational TIROS-N and NOAA-6 satellites now in service. This operational capability has made possible the development of global environmental measurement systems within the temporal sampling constraints of a polar-orbiting satellite. The feasibility of tracking drifting buoys was amply demonstrated by the U.S. Navy and NDBO using the NIMBUS-4 satellite and by the NOAA Atlantic Oceanographic and Meteorological Laboratories, and others, using the EOLE satellite.

The successes of the above-mentioned experiments demonstrated feasibility and utility of polar-orbiting satellite telemetry techniques for low-cost drifting buoy systems to monitor environmental parameters on a worldwide basis, unrestricted by the geographic position measuring limitations of other position-finding systems. The previous satellite system development activities, and particularly the NIMBUS-F satellite system, led to the development and operational implementation

of the present TIROS-N and NOAA-6 satellite systems. The various system elements that comprise the presently available drifting buoy systems are discussed below.

3.1 Communications

The communication and position-fixing capability is central to the success of the utilization of the nonsynoptic, polar-orbiting satellite system. The NIMBUS-F satellite random access measurement system (RAMS) was the prototype to the present operational ARGOS system, and demonstrated the feasibility of using low-cost drifting and other buoy systems as measurement platforms on a global basis. The NIMBUS-F system provided the means of testing the assimilation of nonsynoptic data from various measurement platforms in meeting the scientific objectives of the Global Weather Experiment.

A platform transmit terminal (PTT) was designed to operate on small data collection platforms in concert with the ARGOS system on the TIROS-N and NOAA-6 satellites. The TIROS-N was launched in October 1978, and the NOAA-6 in June 1979. In general, the ARGOS system provides the capability for data collection and position determination for a large number of austere platform configurations. The PTT is particularly applicable to scientific field experiments, providing nonreal-time or asynchronous reporting of low-volume data from low-cost drifting buoys.

The drifting buoy electronics were designed to acquire barometric pressure and sea surface temperature, and to measure internal buoy hull temperature and battery voltage. The data are acquired on a periodic basis and transmitted on a UHF RF link to the ARGOS system aboard the TIROS-N or NOAA-6 polar-orbiting satellites. In operation, all of the sensors are sampled once every two transmit cycles (nominal 40-60 seconds); and transmitted to the satellite for two consecutive transmit cycles for data telemetry integrity verification. Barometric pressure is sampled to provide a nominal 60 second average and the other sensors are sampled for 160 milliseconds. A signal conditioning unit converts the pressure sensor frequency output to a 10-bit binary word. The temperature sensors are conditioned to 8-bit binary words and the battery voltage to a 6-bit binary word. The UHF transmitter generates a stable nominal 401.65 megahertz signal at a nominal power output of 1.5 watts into 50 ohms. Frequency and time diversity allow multiple platform access to the satellite.

The modulation scheme used is split phase PSK to encode data on the transmitted carrier signal. The system is protected from inadvertent continuous transmission as required by the ARGOS specifications. If the transmission continues for one second, the power to the transmitter is interrupted and not re-applied for a period of 16 transmissions.

Platform position is derived from the relative motion between the platform and the satellite, which can be measured by the Doppler frequency shift patterns. All measurements and processing are centrally located, either in the satellite itself or at the earth tracking station, thereby enabling the use of relatively simple systems on small platforms. The system is based on the principle of random access: Each platform transmits at a nominal 40 to 60 second repetition rate, a message containing the identification, sensor values and engineering parameters. Either of the satellites above the horizon of the platform can

receive and record the data for readout to a special ground-based acquisition station. The major acquisition, processing, and dissemination functions are shown in a data flow block diagram in Figure 3. Drifting buoys using the ARGOS system cannot provide synoptic data, but rather data is acquired only when the satellite is in view. All the data are collected at the control data acquisition stations in Gilmore, Alaska, and Wallops Island, Virginia. The received and detected data are then sent to the spacecraft operational control center in Suitland, Maryland, for preliminary processing. The data are then transmitted to the Centre National d'Etudes Spatiales (CNES), an agency of the French government in Toulouse for processing by Service ARGOS. Processed data are then disseminated as appropriate. Meteorological data can be disseminated worldwide over the Global Telecommunications Service (GTS).

The number of successful observations per day is equal to the number of successful locations determined. In polar areas, the position of a buoy is computed using data from two satellites. In the lower latitudes, data provided by one satellite is used for position determination. Figure 4 shows the number of locations that can be processed per day as a function of latitude. Between 0° to 60° latitude, one satellite is used for position determination. In the lower latitudes, the location can be calculated four times a day, using data from two successive orbits of the satellite. In addition, two single passes are available for a total of six observations per day. At about 60° latitude, two successive passes of the same satellite are available about three times per day, but an additional eight observations can be obtained using a one-satellite pass solution. At the high latitudes, greater than 60° latitude, the location is based on two passes of both or successive satellite passes. A maximum of 27 locations per day can be obtained at the poles. The sharp dip in the curve at 82° latitude is due to the inclination of the satellite orbit at 98 degrees. Figure 5 shows the number of orbits during which data from a platform can be expected to be received.

As part of the development program to provide meteorological drifting buoys for the Global Weather Experiment, extensive component and system testing was performed to verify performance prior to procurement of production buoy systems, and deployment of buoys during the experiment. Six prototype buoy systems, which included platform transmit terminals (PTT), were developed for test and evaluation purposes. The PTT was designed to meet the exacting specifications of the ARGOS system and was tested by Service ARGOS for certification to assure noninterference with the ability of the ARGOS system to operate with other platforms, be compatible with the satellite electronics and the ARGOS Processing Center, and be capable of providing location accuracy in accordance with the system specifications. Five prototype systems were evaluated in a controlled test at a fixed location at NDBO for a one-month period. During this period, 224 position fixes were made and the results summarized as follows: The mean radial error for all locations was 0.26 km; the standard deviation of mean radial error was 0.16 km; the largest radial error was 2.15 km; and more than 96 percent of all position fixes were within 0.72 km. The results of the controlled test indicated that the position-fixing capability of the developed PTT and ARGOS system was more than adequate for the location accuracy requirements for anticipated programs. The accuracy exceeded the initial accuracy estimates.¹¹

Figure 3. Data Flow For Drifting Buoy System

Figure 4. Number of Locations per Day as a Function of Latitudes

H MEAN TIME OF VISIBILITY PER DAY, IN HOURS
N NUMBER OF PASSES PER DAY

Figure 5. Number of Orbits per Day During which Data May be Expected to be Received from Buoys

A simplified approximation of the average number of satellite passes per day in view of a buoy is shown in Figure 6. The number of passes depends on the latitude of the buoy and the minimum elevation angle at which the satellite can receive the buoy data. Using operational U.S. FGGE buoy data, the mean number and standard deviation of both good data passes and buoy locations per day were calculated as a function of latitude over a one-month period for buoys located from 20°S to 65°S latitude. Curve A shows the increase in the average number of good data passes per day as the buoy latitude increases. Comparison with the curves in Figure 7 indicates that data re-

ceptions appear to be obtained for buoy elevation angles as low as zero degrees. Curve B in Figure 6 shows the average number of good buoy locations per day as a function of buoy latitude. This curve follows curve A very closely. The buoys transmitted every 51.36 seconds and at least three good transmissions are required to calculate buoy location.

Data from operational drifting buoys were analyzed to determine transmission statistics on all passes for which buoy data were obtained. The average number of transmissions per orbit for passes over five different buoys at various latitudes were

LATITUDE	MEAN NO. OF DATA PASSES/DAY	STANDARD DEVIATION	MEAN NO. OF BUOY LOCATIONS/DAY	STANDARD DEVIATION
20°	4.74	0.94	3.37	0.97
24°S	4.89	0.97	3.63	0.49
29°S	5.11	0.89	3.67	0.68
30°S	5.14	0.79	3.52	0.70
33°S	5.48	0.70	3.85	0.82
40°S	6.19	0.56	4.37	0.84
47°S	7.00	1.00	4.74	0.71
50°S	8.22	0.58	5.07	1.04
51.5°S	8.62	0.79	6.00	1.07
55°S	10.00	0.32	6.41	1.34
55.5°S	10.07	0.47	7.00	1.07
60°S	10.63	0.56	8.30	1.49
64°S	11.37	0.63	9.00	1.07

Figure 6. Average Number of Data Passes and Buoy Locations per Day as a Function of Latitude

calculated, and the results are summarized in Table I below. The overall average was calculated to be 13.43 transmissions per orbit. The maximum number of transmissions received on any sample orbit was 19.

TABLE I
AVERAGE NUMBER OF TRANSMISSIONS PER ORBIT FOR DATA PASSES OVER BUOYS AT VARIOUS LOCATIONS

BUOY ID	LATITUDE	AVERAGE NUMBER OF TRANSMISSIONS PER ORBIT	STANDARD DEVIATION	NUMBER OF ORBITS SAMPLED
1602	44°S	13.07	4.19	100
1608	22°S	13.76	3.97	50
1611	66°S	14.24	4.08	102
1621	45°S	12.93	4.58	60
1634	32°S	13.07	4.30	96
Overall		13.43	4.36	403

3.2 Sensors

Barometric Pressure—Barometric pressure measurements over a 500 km grid in the Southern Oceans were the essential requirement during the Global Weather Experiment. The specifications for the measurement included an accuracy of ± 1 millibar during the expected deployment life of the buoy of one year.^{1,2} The measurement of barometric pressure is probably one of the more difficult measurements to be made from a small and active drifting buoy in the open ocean. The problem of accurately measuring barometric pressure on land in a wind field has been the concern of meteorologists for years. The

added complexity of linear and angular motions, the harsh environment and temperature extremes further complicate the problem. Cost was also a significant consideration. Pressure sensors with inherently good long-term stability characteristics and good repeatability with thermal cycling are expensive devices. The limited power available on a small drifting buoy puts further constraints on the required operational characteristics of the sensor. An initial survey of commercially available sensors indicated that a quartz crystal balance beam transducer, with force proportional to barometric pressure exerted against the beam through a bellows, was the only sensor with the potential to meet all the design constraints. The cost, \$1600 (1978 dollars), however, was a significant portion of the anticipated electronic/sensor system cost. NDBO and the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) studied the problem of providing a suitable barometric pressure sensor meeting FGGE requirements but at a lower cost. Two approaches were considered: A promising commercially available quartz capsule, variable capacitance transducer was chosen for modification to meet FGGE requirements; and an NCAR-developed digital variable capacitance transducer designed around a potentially available stable pressure capsule. Extensive laboratory testing of candidate prototype sensors indicated that the ± 1 millibar, long-term accuracy could not be met by either of the sensors under test. A drift rate of about 1.0 millibar per month was exhibited by the NCAR-developed sensor and a drift rate of about 0.5 millibar per month was exhibited by the quartz capsule variable capacitance transducer.^{1,3}

Figure 7. Average Number of Satellite Passes per Day in View of a Buoy at a Given Latitude for Various Angles Above the Horizon

Because of the limited time remaining during the prototype development phase of the program, the decision was made to use the more costly quartz crystal balance beam transducer. Experience gained during the development and test phases of the program highlighted the importance of an initial, full-range, factory sensor calibration with a sufficient burn-in time to stabilize transducer components. For the FGGE drifting buoy system, the barometric pressure sensor was burned-in for 30 hours at the manufacturer's plant, with a subsequent minimum burn-in period of 150 hours before buoy shipment. Sensor calibration tests were performed during the buoy assembly stages, prior to shipment, and prior to deployment from ship or aircraft.

Prototype buoy sensor performance was established during a field test program from November to December 1978. Pressure data from three buoys were transmitted through the TIROS-N satellite and compared with ground truth standards during satellite overpasses. Differences in the data were calculated and analyzed separately for each buoy under test. Buoy barometric pressure measurements were well within system specifications as shown below in Table II.

TABLE II
STATISTICS ON BUOY BAROMETRIC PRESSURE SENSOR PERFORMANCE

	BUOY 1641	BUOY 1642	BUOY 1643
Barometric Pressure (mb)			
Absolute mean difference between buoy and ground truth	0.54	0.07	0.03
Standard deviation	0.48	0.43	0.46
Number of observations	66	107	115

Postcalibration of the buoy pressure sensors indicated an average calibration shift of 0.2 to 0.3 millibars over the range of pressures measured. This calibration shift was observed over a 12-15 month period.¹⁴

In addition to the development activities leading to the choice of a barometric pressure sensor, the problem of surface pressure measurement from a small buoy subject to a continuous wind field was investigated. An important component of the barometric pressure measurement system is the inlet or pressure port, which allows the ambient pressure to be transmitted freely into the pressure transducer sensing element. The pressure port can be a source of measurement error when exposed to the environment, particularly a wind field. The error or pressure change is related to the shape and configuration of the inlet, and for most configurations, the pressure error is related to the square of the wind velocity. When a port with favorable aerodynamic characteristics is used, rather than terminating the vent with a tube, the wind factor error can be substantially reduced. Two pressure port configurations were developed and tested for the FGGE drifting buoy system. The design goal established for pressure port performance was 1 millibar maximum error at a wind speed for 30 knots with buoy inclinations up to 30 degrees. Two types of pressure port concepts were designed and tested. The first concept considered was the classical parallel plate approach which is an adaptation of the aeronautical engineering approach to measuring static pressure in a wind tunnel. The sensor is generally a flat, smooth plate, with a sharp, burr-free hole drilled in its center perpendicular to the plate surface. This approach was

approximated by the use of two parallel plates of the same dimension with fixed separation so that air could pass smoothly across the inside surface of the plate with the pressure sensing hole in the center of the plate. The performance of the parallel pressure port design was not as good as expected during wind tunnel testing. The pressure error range varied from 1.5 to 7 millibars at about a 10 knot wind speed, depending on the specific design configuration and test attitude.¹⁵

The next approach was to selectively test screened ports to determine if any would perform well enough to continue with design of prototype candidate pressure ports for test and evaluation. The principal of operation is to provide successive layers of screen material to cover the inlet pressure ports of a barometric pressure measuring system to gradually dissipate the kinetic energy component of the scaler pressure component. Remaining would be the static component or true barometric pressure.¹⁶ Tests performed on a variety of porous stone configurations, hollow spheres and cylinders with port holes and perforated sheet steel showed promising results.¹⁵ Worst case pressure errors of 1 millibar were measured at wind speeds up to about 65 knots. Tests performed on a rolled screen pressure port developed by NCAR were very encouraging. One model showed errors of less than 0.8 millibars at wind speeds up to 100 knots and inclination angles up to 20 degrees. These test results looked sufficiently promising to test designs configured for drifting buoy applications. A series of tests were performed to test various screen length and diameter configurations. Wind tunnel pressure error measurements of 1.0 millibar were observed over wind speed ranges of 65 to greater than 100 knots. Four prototype units were constructed to check the ease of fabrication, to perform wind tunnel tests to determine the repeatability of data when units were fabricated using normal production procedures, and to test survival of the pressure port during buoy drop testing. The pressure port performed well; the measurement error ranged from 0.8 to 1.0 millibars at a wind speed of 100 knots normal to the port screen. The pressure port, however, was susceptible to damage during buoy drop tests due to impact with the water. The design concept was reconfigured to reduce the size and mass of the pressure port. A cylindrical-wrapped screen labyrinth covered by a teflon membrane was designed to replace the previous metal screen design. This port was very simple and inexpensive to fabricate. With its low profile, rugged housing, and moderate wind tunnel test results, the pressure port design provided the basis for using this port on all NDBO buoys provided for the Global Weather Experiment. Maximum pressure errors were observed to be 1.0 millibar with wind speeds up to about 45 knots.

Sea Surface Temperature—A thermistor is utilized to measure sea surface temperature about one meter below the nominal waterline of the buoy. The thermistor assembly makes contact with the inside of the main structural hull element, an eight-inch outside diameter 6061 T6 aluminum tube. The sensing transducer is spring-loaded against the wall of the tube for good contact. In essence, an integrated temperature measurement of the submerged hull is achieved. Prototype buoy sensor performance was established during a field test program from November to December 1978. Temperature data from three buoys were transmitted through the TIROS-N satellite and compared with ground truth standards during satellite overpasses. Differences in the data were calculated and analyzed separately for each buoy under test. Buoy sea surface

temperature measurements were well within the system specification of $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and the results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III
STATISTICS ON BUOY SEA SURFACE
TEMPERATURE SENSOR PERFORMANCE

	BUOY 1641	BUOY 1642	BUOY 1643
Water Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)			
Mean Difference Between Buoy and Ground Truth	0.15	0.15	0.40
Standard Deviation	0.32	0.17	0.17
Number of Observations	49	106	107

Subsurface Temperature—As stated above, early development activities to provide a drifting buoy subsurface measurement capability met with less than outstanding success. Three prototype drifting buoy configurations were developed for test and evaluation. The first configuration consisted of a 300-meter armored cable with ten thermistors sensor modules and two Piezo resistive pressure sensor modules. Each transducer module was imbedded in the two-wire electrical cable. Active transducer electronic modules contained a voltage controlled oscillator and were in turn interrogated through the electrical cable. The second configuration consisted of a 200-meter center steel strength member cable with eight electrical conductors connected to four thermistors embedded in the cable. Data acquisition consisted of directly measuring thermistor resistance values. The third configuration consisted of a double armored steel strength exterior member and eight electrical conductors connected to four thermistors embedded in the cable. Mechanically, this was the strongest of the three prototype designs.

Difficulties during deployment of the prototype buoys for field test and evaluation brought to light the need for the development of a self-contained deployment mechanism for these systems. One buoy cable became snagged in such a way on the deck of the ship during deployment that the lower end was cut off to prevent endangering deck personnel. Sensor survival life varied from 20 to 170 days indicating a gradual deterioration of the thermistor line/sensor assemblies. Surprisingly enough, the cable that was severed during deployment survived the longest.

A development effort is now in progress to provide subsurface temperature and pressure measurements to a 200-meter depth. An integral part of the program is the development of a microprocessor for control and on-board computing of data variables. The programmable and versatile microprocessor will also be used for future meteorological and oceanographic drifting buoy applications. Two advanced cable designs are in consideration for the prototype buoys; a braided Kevlar center strength member and a braided Kevlar outer strength member with conductors in the center. Cyclical testing of the line samples are now underway to determine mechanical and electrical failure modes. Part of the design effort is to develop a packaged deployment scheme for the line to provide ease in the ship and air deployment of these systems. A field test program is essential in which the prototype buoys can be recovered for engineering evaluation.

Wind Speed—Wind speed has been measured on drifting buoys with a simple "savonius" rotor-type anemometer. A wind-

driven rotor turns a shaft on which a permanent magnet is mounted. The shaft spins on instrument-type bearings and a detection scheme used to determine the revolutions of the shaft over time, translating the count into wind speed. The major problems experienced to date are those associated with the support bearing life in the harsh sea spray environment buoys are subjected to. Near-term development activities are concentrating on improving the life of the bearings supporting the rotor assembly. Candidate bearing designs and materials are being tested for survival and performance characteristics. The most promising candidates will be tested by mooring or tethering drifting buoys with wind sensors near a ground truth platform in the Gulf of Mexico. It is desired to test these systems over a range of environmental conditions to evaluate their performance.

Field testing of two drifting buoys with an early design wind sensor showed mean errors of -1.6 and -1.4 meters/second during a two-month test period. Errors of this magnitude could be expected, however, due to the difference in height of the wind sensor. Reference ground truth measurements were made at 10 meters above the sea surface, whereas the buoy sensors were only 1.3 meters above the water.¹⁷

Air Temperature—A source of error in an air temperature sensor is the heating effect produced when solar and infrared radiation illuminates the air temperature transducer. Two approaches to solving the radiation problem are being investigated. A small rugged radiation shield has been developed for application on drifting buoys. Laboratory testing has shown that the design requirements for the heating or cooling error of the temperature element as shown below in Table IV can be met.¹⁸ It remains to test and evaluate the air temperature sensor in a field experiment with the developed radiation "shield."

TABLE IV
HEATING OR COOLING ERROR SPECIFICATION

The heating or cooling error shall not exceed:
1. $\pm 3^\circ\text{C}$ at air speeds of 1 to 2 knots.
2. $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ at air speeds of 4 to 10 knots.
3. $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ at all air speeds above 10 knots.

A second approach has been the design of a shield in the configuration of a tube reflective on the outside and absorptive on the inside. The solid wall of the tube acts as an insulator in lieu of a double wall with an air space insulator. Preliminary laboratory testing has shown a steady state error of less than 0.15°C between full shade and sun exposure extremes in still air. A prototype sensor was installed on a drifting buoy and moored near a larger buoy instrumented with a standard NDBO moored buoy meteorological sensor suite. Using the moored buoy air temperature as ground truth, preliminary analysis indicates a one degree difference between the air temperatures reported by both buoys. This difference is not unreasonable considering the probable spatial and temporal variability between the two measurements. This work will continue with additional laboratory and field testing.

3.3 Hull and Power

The drifting buoy hull is a simple spar buoy configuration with a conical flotation buoyancy collar. This development has been a gradual design evolution based on the concept that a hull buoyancy increasing rapidly with draft and with a high

heave resonant frequency would maintain the antenna above the water for optimum telemetry to the satellite. The late Dr. Richardson of Nova University pioneered this basic form, and these form factors are being used today in the hull designs that have evolved. Other design criteria include a low profile to minimize wind drag and a low hull surface drag so the buoy can be used in a drogued configuration with minimal surface current effects.

The major hull elements consist of a lower hull assembly including spar and reserve flotation sections made of aluminum, the antenna housing which is a fiberglass/resin structure and an aluminum electronics rack and spacer assembly containing the electronics, sensors, batteries and ballast weight. The main structural element is a 6061 T6 aluminum, 8-inch diameter tube. The lower end of the tube is closed by a bulkhead welded in place. An aluminum flange is welded to the upper end of the tube forming a mounting bracket for the fiberglass antenna housing. A zinc block, with aluminum attachment strap cast in place, is welded to the lower section of the buoy; forming a sacrificial anode, providing protection from corrosion to any portion of the aluminum hull exposed to seawater due to penetration of the protective paint cover.

Buoyancy is provided by a flotation collar consisting of two aluminum cones welded together and then welded to the tube. The flotation collar chamber is filled with a polyurethane foam. The foam maintains buoyancy if the cone is penetrated.

The power requirements for the electronic system are +12 to +20 volts d.c. at 8 milliamps maximum continuous and 500 milliamps at a 0.006 duty cycle; and +3 volts d.c. at a 0.006 duty cycle. The duty cycle is based on a 60 second transmission repetition rate. The power supply consists of a battery bank of 168 alkaline cells arranged in 14 parallel groups of 12 series cells. The 14 parallel groups are divided into 7 battery modules called pucks and each puck is isolated from the power bus by diodes. An additional puck containing 6 cells is used to provide bias to the regulator switch. The regulator maintains a constant voltage on the UHF transmitter during the transmit cycle. The power supply is adequate to power the buoy for a period of 12 months with additional capacity to provide 4 months shelf life at 25°C.

3.4 Computer Model

A time domain numerical model was developed and is now used to predict the forces within and the motions of buoys and buoy-tether line-drogue systems. Buoy motions and position in the water are simulated and predicted for a specified wind, current, and wave environment.^{19 20} From these simulations, the effectiveness of a drifting buoy system in measuring environmental parameters, data telemetry to the satellite, and measuring water current can be determined. Confidence in the model predictions of system motions have been established through a series of wave tank tests of scale model and full scale buoys.^{21 22}

The numerical model is for planar, two-dimensional motion. Wind, wave, current, and gravity all act in one plane. The responding motion of the buoy is also in the same plane. The equations of motion are based on Newton's second law. Solutions to the fundamental equations are in the time domain and are capable of predicting the response of the buoy to steady

state loads (such as current and wind) and to periodic loads (such as from steady state periodic waves). Large amplitude and nonlinear effects can be simulated. Initially, the buoy is floating at rest with zero trim. Subsequently, the motion from one instant of time to the next is determined by integration of the accelerations, which are determined from all the forces acting on the buoy. These forces include the wind acting on the portion of the buoy above the instantaneous waterline, fluid motion (waves and current) acting on the submerged portion, and gravity. For computations within the program, the buoy is subdivided into elements which have conventional shapes. Drag and added mass forces depend on the relative water motion for each buoy element. The drag force includes two components, one dependent on Reynolds number, the other on Froude number (wave making resistance).

The wind is assumed to be acting horizontally and to be constant with respect to height. For the buoy with no drogue, the current is considered constant with depth.

The wave environment can be specified using either linear wave theory or Dean's stream function wave theory (finite amplitude). Linear wave theory is used in most cases because design waves are often small amplitude in nature and the computational speed of the program is considerably greater with linear wave theory. For near breaking waves, the stream function theory is used. This theory is based on a numerical solution to the Laplace equation and the kinematic and dynamic boundary conditions at the free water surface. The program includes provisions for use of either "breaking" or 3/4 breaking deep water waves. Experimentation has shown that this theory is a good predictor of water particle kinematics within the waves. Particle velocities determined by the appropriate wave theory are superimposed on the specified current.

Inputs to the program include the necessary buoy dimensions and mass properties, the wind, wave, and current environment. The outputs are a tabulation of coordinates, velocities, and accelerations at the specified time intervals and plots of various parameters as a function of time.

A laboratory test program was conducted to validate the numerical model. The test program included impulse response, frequency response, and drift speed tests of full scale and 1/4 scale models. The numerical model was then exercised with the same initial conditions as the impulse response tests. Coefficients of added mass and damping were adjusted until the impulse response curves of the numerical model were the same as the physical tests.

The drift speed was determined for a range of wave periods and amplitudes by measuring the drift distance, the time, and the number of waves. Numerical model predictions of buoy drift speed in waves agreed very well with the results of physical model tests.

In determining the slippage of a drogue relative to a body of water being tracked, the ratio of the product of the drag coefficient and projected area (C_{DA}) of the surface piercing buoy to the (C_{DA}) of the drogue is the critical parameter. Ideally, one would like the ratio to be small, i.e., either the C_{DA} of the surface piercing buoy be very small or the C_{DA} of the drogue

very large. Practical engineering consideration for the present design limit this ratio somewhere between 1/50 and 1/100. Figure 8 shows the slippage error the model predicts under conditions one might expect to be typical in the Southern Oceans.

Figure 8. System Slip Velocity Due to Wind

The model has been used to simulate the slippage of a drogue imbedded in a parcel of water to determine the performance constraints of a Lagrangian measurement system in scientific experiments. Figure 9 shows the drift error predicted for various environmental conditions including wind, waves, and current. Model validation for the Lagrangian measurement portion of the simulation will require an extensive field experiment and is being considered for future work.

3.5 Operational Results

End-to-end test and checkout of the prototype drifting buoy system through the TIROS-N satellite and ARGOS data processing system were initiated prior to the start of the Global Weather Experiment. The results of these tests were successful with the buoys meeting the specified performance goals as reported above. During the Global Weather Experiment, 46 buoys were deployed by five ships between November 1978 and February 1979. Buoy performance was evaluated prior to deployment by activating the buoys prior to a satellite overpass; and comparing the satellite received data with shipboard ground truth data received over radio and hardwire communications links. If buoy sensor data were questionable or out of tolerance, a decision was made whether to deploy the buoy, substitute another buoy, or forego deploying a buoy at the preselected location. After the buoys on a ship had been activated for several days, the pressure differences between individual buoys and the average of three or more buoys sampled at the same time were determined. Good pressure correlation for each of the ships deploying buoys were obtained. The calculated averages of the deviation of the good sensors from the

50-METER TETHER, WINDOWSHADE DROGUE

Figure 9. Lagrangian Drift Error Sensitivity

mean of the sensor values for each satellite pass range from 0.3 to 0.5 millibar standard deviation. The temperature correlation was poor, principally due to varying amounts of solar and other radiation effects. The standard deviation range between ships varied from 0.4 to 1.5°C.

As of March 1980, 22 of the 64 buoys deployed were still operational. The buoys have logged a total of over 15,900 buoy-days of operation, and 10 buoys have exceeded 420 days of operation; the nominal design life of the buoys, not including shelf storage life, is 360 days. The operational success of these meteorological drifting buoys can be attributed in part to the meticulous testing performed during the development phase of the program and the mandatory failure-free, 150-hour burn-in performed on each buoy system prior to deployment. The average time to failure of these buoy systems is 420 days and the average age of the failed buoys is 200 days. Figure 10 shows the cumulative distribution of buoy failures over time during the Global Weather Experiment. The distribution curve will change slightly as the remaining buoys fail in time, but the essence of the statistical information is present and useful for network planning. The failure distribution shown includes all failure modes including deployment failures and buoys drifting up on shore. The percentage of buoys that can be expected to survive as a function of time is shown below in Table V.

TABLE V
PERCENTAGE OF BUOYS EXPECTED TO SURVIVE

After 3 months	70%
After 6 months	56%
After 9 months	50%
After 12 months	40%
After 15 months	34%

CONCLUSION

During the Global Weather Experiment, meteorological drifting buoys proved their worth for surface pressure analysis and also as ground truth for satellites in data-sparse regions of the Southern Hemisphere. The ARGOS data collection system performed nearly perfectly, meeting or exceeding the design specifications. The central processing system proved to be an extremely valuable mechanism for the global near-real time distribution of meteorological parameters from the drifting buoys. In addition to meeting and exceeding the objectives of

Figure 10. Cumulative Distribution of FGGE Buoy Failures

the experiment, drifting buoy data proved to be extremely useful in the improved quality of weather forecast.

Australia has been actively interested in using the data from meteorological drifting buoys for weather forecasting purposes during the experiment. The impact of the data was found to be extremely valuable in overcoming forecasting problems arising from the deficiency of surface observations in the Southern Hemisphere oceans. Australian meteorologists found the buoy data considerably improved the analyses over the oceanic areas and led to improved predictions from the hemisphere numerical model.³

A critical review of the drifting buoy system performance during the experiment found that the overall system had performed very well and had met all expectations. Considering the initial investment, data processing, and deployment, the cost per buoy in place and providing good data during the buoy lifetime was calculated to be about \$65 (1979 dollars) per day, an extremely reasonable figure for data collection at sea.^{2 3}

Plans are underway to continue to use drifting buoys as observational data acquisition platforms. It is fairly certain that drifting buoys will continue to grow as a substantial element in meteorological and oceanographic observing programs during the next decade.

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